

REJUVENATING LIBRARIES FOR INFORMATION ACCESS IN THE DIGITAL ERA

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PUBLICATION PATTERN ANALYSIS IN INDIAN JOURNAL OF INFORMATION SOURCES AND SERVICES (IJISS): A SCIENTOMETRIC APPROACH

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Abstract

Scientometric analysis of 146 research articles published in Indian journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS) has been carried out. Seven Volumes of the journal containing 14 issues from 2011 – 2017 have been taken into consideration for the present study. The number of contributions, authorship pattern & author productivity, average citations, average length of articles, average keywords and collaborative papers has been analyzed. Out of 146 contributions, only 39 are single authored and rest by multi authored with degree of collaboration 0.73 and week collaboration among the authors. Pattern of Co-Authorship revealed that the improving trend of co-authored papers. The study revealed that the author productivity is 0.53 and dominated by the Indian authors.

KEYWORDS: Bibliometrics, Scientometrics, Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services, Author Productivity, Collaboration pattern.

1.0 Introduction

Scientometrics is a discipline which analyses scientific publications to explore the structure and growth of science. The bibliometric/Scientometric/informetric techniques used to analyze various quantitative or qualitative aspects of a publication. It is a scientific field that studies the evolution of science through some quantitative measures of scientific information, as the number of scientific articles published in a given period of time, their citation impact, etc. The history of science and technology, philosophy of science and sociology of scientific knowledge are the related fields of Scientometrics.

The term scientometrics is often used with the meaning as the bibliometrics, originated in Russia. The application of quantitative methods to the history of science,

Scientometrics is the science of measuring the science, which involves counting artefacts to the production & use of information and arriving conclusions from the counts. Bibliometrics / Scientometrics research includes studies related to the scattering & growth of literature, author productivity, obsolescence of documents, distribution of scientific literature by country, by language, etc, which helps to monitor the growth & pattern of research.(Pritchard, 1969)¹ described the Bibliometrics as the application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other media. Scientometric research is devoted to quantitative studies of science and technology (Van Raan, 1997)².Scientometrics applies the bibliometric techniques to science and examines the development of the sciences. (Virgil, 1994)³.Main areas of Scientometrics are individual scientific documents, authors, scientific institutions, academic journals and regional aspects of science (Stock & Sonja, 2006)⁴

In this paper, an attempt has been made to analyze the contributions to Indian Journal Information Sources and Services (IJISS) published during the year 2011 – 2017, in order to explore the author pattern, collaborative research, keywords and length of the papers among the contributions. This study covers the 146 articles of 14 issues published.

2.0 Source of Study

Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS) was selected as the source journal for the present research study. Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS) is a popular journal of library and information science (LIS) in India. IJISS was started in 2010 as half yearly journal. With a gap of 8 years, fourteen issues were published up to 2017.

Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS) a Multidisciplinary Library and Information Science Journal is a refereed Journal and it publishes from India. This Journal encompasses all branches of Library and Information Sciences and its sub – disciplines like Library Management; Information Systems & Services, Information Processing & Retrieval; Information Sources & Services; Community Information System, Scientometrics & Informetrics, IR Theory, Knowledge Organization; Information processing & retrieval, Classification, Preservation &

Conservation, Information Management, Library classification, Information sources, Systems and Services, Computer Application in Library; Digital Library; Information Systems; Bibliographic Control, etc.

3.0 Review of Related Literature

Scientometric/Bibliometric/Citation studies have done earlier by different authors on the different individual journal publications and literature on specific subject areas. The following studies related to the objectives of this study have been reviewed. (Srimurugan & Nattar, 2009)⁵ analyzed the D-LIB magazine published during 2000 – 2007 which revealed that highest number of paper was published in 2005 and the lowest in 2007. (Vijay & Raghavan, 2007)⁶ analyzed the Journal of Food Science & Technology published during 2000 – 2004 and found that above 93% of contributions were by multiple authors.

A Scientimetric Analysis on Indian Journal of Physics was made by (Nattar, 2009)⁷ during 2004 – 2008 which revealed that the year 2004 records the highest % of contributions regarding single, two and three authored. Kannappanavar B U, Swamy C & Vijay Kumar M (2004)⁸ analyzed the publishing trends of Indian Chemical Scientists during 1996 – 2000, which revealed average number of authors per paper has increased from 7.52 to 8.39. An attempt was made by Tilak Hazarika, Kusuma Goswami & Pritimoni Das (2003)⁹ to analyze the contributions of Indian Forester which found Degree of Collaboration was 0.64 among the authors. Guan & Ma (2007)¹⁰ examined the China's Semiconductor Literature and found mega authored papers records the higher value for Co-Authorship Index.

Senthamilselvi & Srinivasa Raghavan (2010)¹¹ analyzed the issues of IEEE Trans on Power Electronics published during 2006 – 2008 which revealed that maximum number of papers was published between 6 – 10 pages category. A bibliometric study has been carried out by Kalyane V L and Sen B K (1995)¹² on the Journal of Oilseeds Research published during 1984 – 1992 which revealed that the keyword "Groundnut" tops the list with 53 records. Sanni S A and Zainab A N (2010)¹³ examined the contributions published in Medical Journal of Malaysia during 2004 – 2008 and found 4.82% (28) of contributions were published by Malaysian authors with foreign collaboration.

4.0 Objectives of the Study

The following objectives of this study are formulated for the purpose of present study

- To map the year wise distribution of papers
- To examine the authorship pattern & author productivity
- To determine the degree of collaboration
- To assess the pattern of Co-Authorship
- To identify collaborative pattern
- To find the average length of papers
- To find the average keywords

5.0 Scope And Methodology

The present study tries to find out the literature growth, authorship and collaboration pattern, average length of articles and average keywords included in the source journal. Seven Volumes (Vol. No.1 to No.7) of Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS), published between 2011 and 2017 containing 14 issues have been taken into consideration to the present study.

A datasheet was prepared in MS-Excel to record the data and then the data was entered manually into it from the journal itself. The details regarding number of papers, nature of author, keywords and length of papers are collected to fulfill the objectives of the present study. The collected data was analyzed with the following bibliometric indicators.

- Extent of Authorship Pattern (Single vs. Multiple)
- Degree of Collaboration
- Co-Authorship Index

6.0 Limitations

- The study includes open source journal in particular Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS) among other journals.
- This study is limited to research papers published in Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS) between the periods 2011 and 2017 only.

7.0 Results And Discussion

7.1 Year wise distribution of papers

Table 1 shows the distribution of research articles published in Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services during 2011 – 2017. The total of 146 research articles was published with an average of 20.86 articles per year. Out of 146 articles, the highest number of research articles were published in the year 2012 with 29 research articles (14.5 articles per issue) followed by the 2011 ; 27 articles, 2014 ; 25 articles, 2017 ; 19 articles and the lowest number of articles were published in the year 2015 and 2016 with 14 articles each (7 articles per issue).

Year	Vol. No.	No. Of Issues	Total Papers	Percentage	Cum No. Of Papers	Percent of Cum Total
2011	1	2	27	18.49	27	18.49
2012	2	2	29	19.86	56	38.36
2013	3	2	18	12.33	74	50.68
2014	4	2	25	17.12	99	67.81
2015	5	2	14	9.59	113	77.40
2016	6	2	14	9.59	127	86.99
2017	7	2	19	13.02	146	100.00
Total		14	146	100		

7.2 Authorship Pattern

The table 2 presents the data according to rank. It is observed from the Table 2 about 73% of papers were contributed by multi authors. Out of 146 papers, the highest numbers of papers were published by double authors and it accounts for 84 with 57.53% followed by single authored articles account for 39 with 26.71%. 14.38% of articles were published by three authors. 1.37 % of articles were published by four &

above authors. But the trend of the author pattern in the journal shows that the team size was two to three.

Rank	Authors	No. Of Papers	%	Cum No of Papers	Cum %
1	Two	84	57.53	84	57.53
2	Single	39	26.71	123	84.25
3	Three	21	14.38	144	98.63
4	Four & Above	2	1.37	146	100
	Total	146	100%		

7.3 Authorship Pattern in accordance with year wise

The data pertaining to authorship pattern year wise have been given in the Table No.3. Regarding single authored contributions, the years 2012 & 2011 have the highest contributions with 12 and 8 each and 6 in year 2015 and 4 in the year 2014 & 2017 and lowest 2 in the year 2016. Regarding double authored contributions, the year 2014 has the highest contributions with 17. The year 2011 has the highest contributions regarding three authored contributions with 6 and 2012. The year 2011 & 2014 has the highest contributions of four authored (more than three authors) with 1 each.

Year	Authors				Total
	1	2	3	4	
2011	8	12	6	1	27
2012	12	14	3	0	29
2013	3	13	2	0	18
2014	4	17	3	1	25
2015	6	6	2	0	14
2016	2	10	2	0	14
2017	4	12	3	0	19
Total	39	84	21	2	146

7.4 Author Productivity

The data pertaining to author productivity has presented in the Table 4. The table shows that the total average number of authors per paper is 1.89 for the 146

articles. The years 2013 & 2017 has the relatively equal average number of authors per article when compared the total average number of authors per article. The average productivity per author is 0.53 during the year 2011 - 2017. The years 2013 & 2017 has the relatively equal productivity per author when compared to the average productivity. Productivity has been calculated with the following formula (Fuyuki, 2009)¹⁴

Average Authors per Paper = No. of Authors / No. of Papers

Productivity per Author = No. of Papers / No. of Authors

Table 4 - Author Productivity - year wise					
S.No.	Year	Total No. of Papers	Total No. of Authors	AAPP	Productivity per Author
1	2011	27	54	2	0.5
2	2012	29	47	1.62	0.62
3	2013	18	35	1.94	0.51
4	2014	25	51	2.04	0.49
5	2015	14	24	1.71	0.58
6	2016	14	28	2	0.5
7	2017	19	37	1.95	0.51
Total		146	276	1.89	0.53

7.5 Degree of Collaboration

In order to determine the strength of Collaboration (DC), the following formula suggested by (Subramanyam, 1993)¹⁵ has been employed.

$$DC = N_m / (N_m + N_s)$$

Where, DC = Degree of Collaboration

N_m = Number of Multiple Authored Papers

N_s = Number of Single Authored Papers

The Degree of Collaboration of authors by year wise is presented in the Table 5. The degree of collaboration ranges from 0.74 to 0.93. The average degree of collaboration is 0.73 during the period 2011 - 2017 and it brings out clearly that there exists a high level of collaboration in the journal.

Table 5 : Degree of Collaboration - year wise					
S.No.	Year	N_s	N_m	N_s + N_m	DC
1	2011	8	46	54	0.85
2	2012	12	35	47	0.74
3	2013	3	32	35	0.91
4	2014	4	47	51	0.92
5	2015	6	18	24	0.75
6	2016	2	26	28	0.93
7	2017	4	33	37	0.89
Total		39	107	146	0.73

7.6 Pattern of Co-Authorship

In order to assess the Pattern of Co-Authorship (CAI), the following formula suggested by (Garg and Padhi, 1999)¹⁶ has been employed.

Where,

N_{ij} = Number of papers having authors in block i

N_{io} = Total output of block i

N_{oj} = Number of papers having j authors for all blocks

N_{oo} = Total number of papers for all authors and all blocks

CAI = 100 implies that a country's co-authorship effort for a particular type of authorship corresponds to the world average, CAI > 100 reflects higher than average co-authorship effort, and CAI < 100 lower than average co-authorship effort by that country for a given type of authorship pattern.

For calculating the co-authorship index for authors, countries have been replaced by block. For this study, the authors have been classified into four blocks, viz Single, Two, Three and more than three authors and the results of Co-authorship index as per the formula have been presented in the Table No.6.

Table 6 : Pattern of Co-Authorship - year wise						
S.No.	Year	Single Author	Two Authors	Three Authors	>Three Authors	Total

		No	CAI	No	CAI	No	CAI	No	CAI	
1	2011	8	55	12	38	6	77	1	135	27
2	2012	12	95	14	51	3	44	0	0	29
3	2013	3	33	13	66	2	40	0	0	18
4	2014	4	29	17	57	3	41	1	143	26
5	2015	6	93	6	43	2	57	0	0	14
6	2016	2	26	2	12	2	49	0	0	6
7	2017	4	40	12	56	3	56	0	0	19
Total		39		84		21		2		146

It is observed from the Table 6, the CAI for single authors is declined from 55 in the year 2011 to 40 in the year 2017. On the other hand, the CAI for double authors is enhanced from 38 in the year 2011 to 56 in the year 2017, which indicates the pattern of co authorship is increasing among the contributions of the journal. On the other hand, there is a fluctuation trend of CAI for multi authored contributions. The similar type of result has been drawn by Jeysankar R, et al in the Current Science. (Jeysankar, 2009)¹⁷

7.7 Distribution of Pages

Table 7 shows that 146 papers published with a total page of 817 (average 5.60 pages per article) during the year 2011 – 2017. It is observed that the average length of the articles varied from a minimum of 4.41 pages to a maximum of 11.67 pages. The year 2016 has highest average page per paper with 7.07 pages while the year 2012 has the lowest average page per paper with 4.41.

Table 7 - Distribution of Pages - year wise							
S.No.	Year	No. of Articles	Total Pages	Average Pages Per Article	Percentage	Cum No. of Pages	Cum %
1	2011	27	154	5.7	18.85	154	18.85

2	2012	29	128	4.41	15.67	282	34.52
3	2013	18	97	5.39	11.87	379	46.39
4	2014	25	145	5.8	17.75	524	64.14
5	2015	14	99	7.07	12.12	623	76.25
6	2016	14	82	5.86	10.04	705	86.29
7	2017	19	112	5.89	13.71	817	100.00
Total		146	817	5.60			

7.8 Average Keywords per Article

Table 8 reveals that 581 keywords have been appended to 146 papers. It is observed that the average keyword of the paper varied from a minimum of 3.14 to a maximum of 4.53 during the year 2011 – 2017. The year 2017 has the highest average keyword per paper with 4.53 keywords per paper while the year 2012 has the lowest average keywords per paper with 3.14. The overall average keywords per article are 3.98.

S. No.	Year	No. of Articles	Total Keywords	Average Keywords per Paper	Cum No. of keywords	Percent of Cum Total
1	2011	27	97	3.59	97	16.70
2	2012	29	91	3.14	188	32.36
3	2013	18	80	4.44	268	46.13
4	2014	25	110	4.4	378	65.06
5	2015	14	59	4.21	437	75.22
6	2016	14	58	4.14	495	85.20
7	2017	19	86	4.53	581	100
Total		146	581	3.98		

7.9 Distribution of Indian and Foreign Contributions

Table 9 shows that out of 146 articles, 138 (94.52%) articles published by Indian Authors followed by International Authors with 6 Articles (4.11%). Only 2 (1.37%) articles published by Indian Authors collaborated with international Authors and similar type of study has been conducted by (Zainab A N, et al, 2009)¹⁸. It seems that there was poor collaboration of Indian Authors with Foreign Authors. It is observed from the data that out of 14 issues, 8 issues having the contributions only by Foreign Authors.

Table 9 - Distribution of Indian and Foreign Contributions				
Form	Contributions	%	Cumulative Contributions	Cum %
Indian Authors	138	94.52	138	94.52
Indian Authors with Foreign Collaboration	2	1.37	140	95.89
Foreign Authors	6	4.11	146	100
Total	146			

8.0 Findings and Conclusion

The study has revealed the findings which will be useful to information managers and persons associated with Indian Journal of Information Sources and Services (IJISS). The maximum number of papers published in the year 2012 and minimum in the years 2015 & 2016. The highest number of research papers found in the study by multiple authors during the study period. The degree of collaboration found was 0.73. It is found that the average value for CAI was around 40 during the study period and it reflects below than the world average. It is an alarming state that effort should be made on par with world average. The author productivity is 0.53 and the average number of authors per paper found in the present study is 1.89. The average pages per paper observed in the study is 5.60 as the total numbers of pages are 817 with 146 papers. The average keywords per paper observed in the study are 3.98 as the total number of keywords are 581. The majority of the contributions are by Indian Authors (94.52%). Papers by Indian Authors with Foreign Collaboration are minimal (1.37% of articles).

The findings have focused that the majority of papers by multi authors and Indian authors. There was poor international collaboration by Indian authors. The average page is 5.60 and it is the ideal for research papers. The Degree of collaboration (using Subramanyam's formula) indicates that there exists a high degree of collaboration. The average Co-Authorship Index for all the authors reflects the world average in the journal and improving trend of co-authored papers. The study revealed that the journal seems to be not popular among the international research community with around 4.11% of papers.

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